

Prevalence of Tobacco Use among Psychiatric Patients at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Western India

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Abstract:

Introduction: Tobacco use disorder is a global health concern, causing eight million deaths annually and significantly impacting disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). The prevalence of tobacco use disorder is 2–4 times higher among psychiatric patients. Youth with tobacco use disorder often have high rates of ADHD, bipolar disorder, anxiety, depression, and schizophrenia, and consume tobacco more than healthy individuals. This study aimed to examine the prevalence and severity of tobacco use and access to tobacco cessation among psychiatric patients in a tertiary care hospital in Gujarat.

Materials & Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted among 400 psychiatric patients at a tertiary care psychiatric hospital in Gujarat. A consecutive sampling technique was used, and informed consent was obtained from each participant. Demographic and clinical data were collected using a pre-designed proforma, and the Tobacco Craving Questionnaire-Short Form (TCQ-SF) was used to measure tobacco cravings.

Results: The prevalence of tobacco use among psychiatric patients was notably high at 45%. Schizophrenia-related disorders were more prevalent (38.3%) compared to mood disorders (26.3%), behavioral syndromes (18.0%), and anxiety and stress-related disorders (17.5%). Higher tobacco use was observed among males, divorced or widowed individuals, those with lower education, employed individuals, and rural residents. Despite the psychiatric setting, the assessment and implementation of interventions for tobacco cessation or reduction remained suboptimal.

Conclusion: To address the high prevalence of tobacco use among psychiatric patients, comprehensive screening should be enhanced across all patient groups, with targeted cessation programs for high-risk populations such as males, divorced or widowed individuals, and employed individuals. Training for healthcare providers on effective cessation strategies is essential, and inpatient admissions should be utilized as opportunities for screening and intervention.

Keywords: Craving, Mood disorders, Tobacco cessation, Tobacco use, schizophrenia, Substance use.

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Introduction

Tobacco use disorder is a global health concern and a modern epidemic, often referred to as "the brown plague." Globally, tobacco use causes eight million deaths annually and contributes to 6% and 5% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) from smokeless tobacco and cigarette smoking, respectively. [1,2] In India, NFHS-5 (2019-21) found that 38% of males and 9% of females over 15 years use tobacco. [3] India reports one million tobacco-related deaths annually, accounting for one-sixth of global tobacco deaths. Tobacco-related mortality and morbidity are expected to rise significantly by 2050. [4] Tobacco products can be smoked (cigarettes, cigars, bidis, hookah, pipes) or chewed (khaini, gutka, pan with tobacco, betel nut). In India, the most common forms of tobacco use among men are chewing pan masala or gutka (15%),

smoking cigarettes (13%), using khaini (12%), and smoking bidis (7%). [3]

Nicotine, the primary chemical in tobacco, induces both physical and psychological dependence and accelerates the metabolism of psychotropic medications. [5] Smoking significantly influences the metabolism of psychotropic medications. Nicotine being a hepatic cytochrome enzyme inducer, increases the metabolism of psychotropic medications, thereby decreasing their efficacy. It particularly impacts the effectiveness of antidepressants, antipsychotics, and benzodiazepines. Additionally, nicotine is associated with respiratory, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, urogenital diseases, and numerous malignancies. [6]

The prevalence of tobacco use disorder (smoking) is found to be 2–4 times higher among patients with psychiatric disorders, including other substance use disorders. [7] Youth with tobacco use disorder often experience high rates of attention-deficit hyperkinetic disorder, bipolar affective disorder, anxiety disorders, depression, and schizophrenia, consume tobacco in higher rates than healthy individuals. [8] Additionally, patients with psychiatric disorders frequently smoke to alleviate symptoms, and chronic smoking significantly reduces life expectancy. Comorbid psychiatric disorders in tobacco users contribute to relapses and the persistence of tobacco use despite quit attempts. [7,8] Tobacco users with depression as compared to non-depressed tobacco users experience greater difficulty in quitting. [5]

Despite psychiatrists' training in addiction management, smoking cessation advice is given to patients with SMI at similar rates as the general population, even in developed countries. In India, the rates may be lower due to a shortage of mental health professionals and the high patient load in public hospitals. Consultations often focus on the primary mental health condition rather than tobacco cessation, although in-patient consultations offer an opportunity for assessment and intervention despite diagnostic overshadowing. [9] Among the Indian population, there are cultural as well as geographical variations in the extent and pattern of tobacco use in psychiatric patients. This study explored the prevalence of tobacco use among psychiatric in-patients at a tertiary care hospital in Western India and compared sociodemographic and clinical parameters between tobacco users and nonusers.

Materials & Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted at a tertiary care psychiatric hospital in Gujarat, following approval from the institutional ethics committee, from January 2022 to June 2023.

Determination of sample size was done using the formula,

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{L^2}$$

Where

- $Z = 1.96$ at 95% confidence level;
- $p =$ prevalence of tobacco use in psychiatric patients of Badekar et al.⁹ (34%), $p = 0.34$;
- $q = 1-p = 66\% = 0.66$;
- $L =$ Absolute precision/margin of error (5%). = 0.05.

Using these values, the calculated sample size was 345. This number was inflated by 10% to account for nonresponse, incomplete responses, refusals, and withdrawals, resulting in a minimum sample size of 370. Ultimately, 400 patients were enrolled in the study.

A consecutive sampling technique was employed to select the study sample. Informed consent was obtained from each participant. The study included psychiatric diagnoses such as schizophrenia, bipolar affective disorders, substance use disorders, neurotic disorders, and others, encompassing both male and female patients. Patients with significant head injuries, prominent cognitive deficits, those admitted primarily for other addictive disorders, and those with intellectual disabilities were excluded.

A total of 400 patients were enrolled in the study. Demographic details such as age, sex, education level, occupation, marital status, and residency; tobacco use and primary psychiatric diagnoses were collected using pre designed proforma. "Current tobacco use" was empirically defined as tobacco use within the past 30 days before the assessment. Tobacco Craving Questionnaire-Short Form (TCQ-SF) was used to measure the intensity and frequency of tobacco cravings.¹⁰

Statistical Analysis: The data was entered in Microsoft Excel 2016 and analyzed with Epi info version 7.1.4.0 Continuous data was presented with mean and standard deviation while nominal data was presented with frequency and percentage. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was used to check data normality. Comparisons between various groups were conducted using the independent t test and ANOVA test for continuous variables and the Chi-square test for discrete variables. A level of $p < 0.05$ was considered as significance.

Results

Figure 1: Prevalence of Tobacco user among psychiatric patients

Out of 400 psychiatric patients, 180 (45.0%) patients used tobacco, 82 (20.5%) used smokeless tobacco, 65 (16.3%) were exclusive smokers, and 33 (8.3%) used both forms of tobacco.

Table 1: Prevalence of Tobacco user and pattern of tobacco use among patients different psychiatric disease.

Psychiatric disease	F20-29	F30-39	F40-49	F50-59	p value
Total (n=400)	153 (38.3%)	105 (26.3%)	70 (17.5%)	72 (18.0%)	
Tobacco non user (n=245)	90 (58.8%)	56 (53.3%)	37 (52.9%)	37 (51.4%)	0.67
Tobacco user (n=155)	63 (41.2%)	49 (46.7%)	33 (47.1%)	35 (48.6%)	
Smokeless tobacco user	30 (19.6%)	23 (21.9%)	15 (21.4%)	14 (19.4%)	0.26
Exclusive smokers	25 (16.3%)	20 (19%)	10 (14.3%)	10 (13.9%)	
Both forms of tobacco	8 (5.2%)	6 (5.7%)	8 (11.4%)	11 (15.3%)	

The patient population was categorized into four primary psychiatric disease groups according to ICD 10: F 20-29 (schizophrenia, schizotypal, and delusional disorders, 153, 38.3%), F 30-39 (mood disorders including depression and bipolar disorders, 105, 26.3%), F 40-49 (neurotic, anxiety, stress-related, and somatoform disorders, 17.5%), and F 50-59 (behavioural syndromes associated with physiological disturbances and physical factors, 72, 18.0%). Total 258 patients (64.5%) had serious mental illness (SMI; F 20-29 and F 30-39) and 142 patients had chronic mental illness (CMI; F 40-49 and F 50-59).

Prevalence of tobacco use was not significantly different among different psychiatric disease as 41.2% among patients with F 20-29 diseases, 46.7% among patients with F 30-39 diseases, 47.1% among patients with F 40-49 diseases and 48.6% among patients with F 50-59 diseases (p = 0.67). Pattern of tobacco use (smokeless tobacco user, exclusive smoker and dual users) was not significantly different among patients with different psychiatric disease (p = 0.26).

The mean age of the psychiatric patients was 38.1 ± 9.82 years. Of these patients, 68% were male, 46.75% were married, 36% had a primary or lesser education, and 46.75% were unemployed. The majority, 64%, resided in semi-urban or urban areas. Notably, 29.5% had a history of suicide attempts, 46% had previous hospitalizations, 46.5% used other psychoactive substances, and 21.75% had substance use disorders.

A significantly higher proportion of males were tobacco users (59.6%) compared to females (14.1%), with an odds ratio (OR) of 9.0 (95% CI: 5.17 to 15.66). Divorced or widow individuals (58.0%) were more likely to use tobacco compared to married (41.8%) and unmarried individuals (43.3%), with an OR of 1.88 (95% CI: 1.13 to 3.18). Individuals with primary or lesser education had a higher tendency to use tobacco, approaching statistical significance. Unemployed individuals (32.1%) were less likely to use tobacco than employed individuals (56.8%), with an OR of 2.85 (95% CI: 1.85 to 4.34). Tobacco use was more prevalent in rural areas (52.8%) compared to semi-urban/urban areas (40.6%), with an OR of 1.63 (95%

CI: 1.08 to 2.46). There was no significant difference in tobacco use based on religion, age, type of family.

Individuals using other psychoactive substances had a significantly higher prevalence of tobacco use (72.6%), with an OR of 9.94 (95% CI: 6.27 to

15.75). Those with substance use disorders (72.4%) were significantly more likely to use tobacco, with an OR of 4.39 (95% CI: 2.60 to 7.41). No significant difference in tobacco use was found based on a history of suicidal attempts and previous hospitalization.

Table 2: Comparison of various characteristics of psychiatric patients among tobacco users and tobacco non user.

	Tobacco user (n=155)	Tobacco non user (n=245)	Total (n=400)	% out of 400	p value	OR (95% CI)
Age	39.1 ± 10.1	37.2 ± 11.3	38.1 ± 9.82		0.56	
Gender						
Male	162 (59.6%)	110 (40.4%)	272 (100%)	68.0	< 0.001	9.0 (5.17 to 15.66)
Female	18 (14.1%)	110 (85.9%)	128 (100%)	32.0		
Marital status						
Married	81 (43.3%)	106 (56.7%)	187 (100%)	46.8	0.02	1.88 (1.13 to 3.18)
Unmarried	59 (41%)	85 (59%)	144 (100%)	36.0		
Others	40 (58%)	29 (42%)	69 (100%)	17.3		
Religion						
Hindu	148 (44.2%)	187 (55.8%)	335 (100%)	83.8	0.53	0.81 (0.48 to 1.39)
Others	32 (49.2%)	33 (50.8%)	65 (100%)	16.3		
Education						
Primary or lesser	74 (51.4%)	70 (48.6%)	144 (100%)	36.0	0.06	1.49 (0.99 to 2.25)
Matriculation and above	106 (41.4%)	150 (58.6%)	256 (100%)	64.0		
Occupation						
Unemployed	60 (32.1%)	127 (67.9%)	187 (100%)	46.8	< 0.001	2.85 (1.85 to 4.34)
Employed	121 (56.8%)	92 (43.2%)	213 (100%)	53.3		
Residence						
Rural	76 (52.8%)	68 (47.2%)	144 (100%)	36.0	0.02	1.63 (1.08 to 2.46)
Semi-urban/urban	104 (40.6%)	152 (59.4%)	256 (100%)	64.0		
Type of family						
Nuclear	144 (44.7%)	178 (55.3%)	322 (100%)	80.5	0.91	NA
Extended Nuclear	22 (47.8%)	24 (52.2%)	46 (100%)	11.5		
Joint	14 (43.8%)	18 (56.3%)	32 (100%)	8.0		
Suicidal attempt						
Yes	56 (47.5%)	62 (52.5%)	118 (100%)	29.5	0.59	1.15 (0.74 to 1.77)
No	124 (44%)	158 (56%)	282 (100%)	70.5		
Previous hospitalization						
Yes	76 (41.3%)	108 (58.7%)	184 (100%)	46.0	0.20	0.75 (0.50 to 1.13)
No	104 (48.1%)	112 (51.9%)	216 (100%)	54.0		
Any other psychoactive substance use						
Yes	135 (72.6%)	51 (27.4%)	186 (100%)	46.5	< 0.001	9.94 (6.27 to 15.75)
No	45 (21%)	169 (79%)	214 (100%)	53.5		
Substance use disorders						
Yes	63 (72.4%)	24 (27.6%)	87 (100%)	21.8	< 0.001	4.39 (2.60 to 7.41)
No	117 (37.4%)	196 (62.6%)	313 (100%)	78.3		

Table 3: Tobacco related characteristics of all psychiatric patients

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age of initiation of tobacco use		
<18 years	57	31.7
>18 years	123	68.3
Nicotine dependence (current)	58	32.2
Not been asked about tobacco use	80	44.4
Not advised about Quit	67	37.2
Provided assistance	43	23.9
Provided with NRTs or anti-crav- ing medications	38	21.1

Among 180 tobacco user in patients with psychiatric disease, 57 (31.7%) initiated tobacco use before the age of 18. Currently, 58 (32.2%) exhibit nicotine dependence. Total 80 (44.4%) of patients were not asked about their tobacco use, and 67 (37.2%) were not advised to quit. Only 43 (23.9%) received assistance to quit, and 38 (21.1%) were provided with nicotine replacement therapies (NRTs) or anti-craving medications.

Table 4: Reasons for tobacco use among psychiatric patients by user type and perception of psych activity

Reason for tobacco use	Exclusive smokers (n=65)	Smoke-less tobacco user (n=82)	Dual user (n=33)	p value
Enjoyment	10 (15.4%)	8 (9.8%)	5 (15.2%)	0.96
Fashionable	3 (4.6%)	3 (3.7%)	1 (3%)	
Friends	37 (56.9%)	39 (47.6%)	16 (48.5%)	
Experiment	9 (13.8%)	22 (26.8%)	8 (24.2%)	
Stress	6 (9.2%)	10 (12.2%)	4 (12.1%)	
Do you think tobacco products are psychoactive substances				
Yes	52 (80%)	55 (67.1%)	25 (75.8%)	0.01
No	6 (9.2%)	23 (28%)	7 (21.2%)	
Don't know	9 (13.8%)	4 (4.9%)	1 (3%)	

Primary reasons for tobacco use among psychiatric patients include influence from friends, experimentation, and stress relief, with slight variations between groups. A significant majority of exclusive smokers (80%) recognize tobacco as a psychoactive substance, compared to smokeless users (67.1%) and dual users (75.8%), highlighting differing perceptions among these groups.

TCQ-SF was used to assess the intensity and nature of tobacco cravings in individuals with SMI and

CMI. The results were compared across four main dimensions: Emotionality, Expectancy, Compulsivity, and Purposefulness. Both groups had similar median scores in Emotionality (12.0), Expectancy (14.0), Compulsivity (10.0 for SMI, 9.5 for CMI), and Purposefulness (12.0). The total craving scores were also comparable, with median scores of 47.0 for SMI and 46.0 for CMI. Patients in both groups have moderate craving for tobacco.

Table 5: Tobacco Craving Questionnaire (TCQ-SF) scores among individuals with serious and chronic mental illness

TCQ component	Serious mental illness	Chronic Mental illness	p value
Emotionality	12.0 (10.0-13.0)	12.0 (12.0-13.25)	> 0.05
Expectancy	14.0 (13.0-15.0)	14.0 (10.75-15.0)	> 0.05
Compulsivity	10.0 (9.0-14.0)	9.50 (7.0-10.0)	> 0.05
Purposefulness	12.0 (11.0-14.0)	12.0 (10.0-14.0),	> 0.05
Total	47.0 (40.0-67.0)	46.0 (38.0 to 68.0)	> 0.05

Discussion

Socio-demographic profile

The socio-demographic profile of 400 psychiatric patients in our study showed a mean age of 38.1 years, with 68% males and 46.7% married. About 36% had primary or lower education, and 46.75% were unemployed, while 64% lived in semi-urban or urban areas. These trends align with findings from other studies, indicating consistent socio-demographic patterns among psychiatric patients.

Badekar et al. [9] found that 60.2% of their 500 patients were male, 54.6% were married, and 48% had education below the primary level, with a high rate of unemployment (59%) and a significant proportion from semi-urban backgrounds (47.6%). Swetha P et al. [10] reported 63% males with a mean age of 33.09 years, 43.5% married, and a majority from nuclear families (73.5%) and urban areas (60%).

Clinical profile

In our study, psychiatric patients were classified according to ICD-10 into four groups: schizophrenia, schizotypal, and delusional disorders (38.3%); mood disorders (26.3%); neurotic, anxiety, stress-related, and somatoform disorders (17.5%);

and behavioral syndromes associated with physiological disturbances (18.0%). Significant proportions were diagnosed with serious mental illness (64.5%)—including schizophrenia and mood disorders—and chronic mental illness (35.5%)—comprising neurotic and behavioral disorders.

Similarly, Badekar et al. [9] reported schizophrenia, schizotypal, and delusional disorders in 42.6%, mood disorders in 48.4%, neurotic, anxiety, stress-related, and somatoform disorders in 7.8% and behavioral syndromes associated with physiological disturbances in 1.2% patients. Comparatively, Swetha P et al.¹⁰ identified schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders as the most frequent psychiatric diagnoses (41.5%), followed by mood disorders (26.5%), substance use disorders (18.5%), and neurotic, stress-related, and somatoform disorders (6.0%).

Prevalence of tobacco use

This study reveals a high prevalence of tobacco use among psychiatric patients, with 45% of the 400 surveyed individuals identified as tobacco users. Earlier studies by Badekar et al.⁹ and Swetha P et al. [10] reported similar prevalence rates ranging from 34% to 39.5%.

Compared to the general population in India, where tobacco use is 28.5%, psychiatric patients exhibit significantly higher rates, posing elevated risks of morbidity and mortality from tobacco-related medical conditions.¹⁰ In Western studies, tobacco use prevalence ranges from 50% to 80%, reflecting cultural, economic, and accessibility differences compared to India and underscoring the global variation in tobacco use patterns. [11,12]

Our findings also highlight diverse tobacco use behaviors among psychiatric patients, with 20.5% using smokeless tobacco, 16.3% smoking exclusively, and 8.3% using both forms. Badekar et al. [9] found 21% using exclusive smokeless tobacco, 40% exclusive smokers, and 39% dual users, highlighting diverse tobacco use patterns within psychiatric populations. Swetha P et al. [10] reported 18.5% smokers, 13.0% smokeless tobacco users, and 8.0% dual users, with a significant majority (88%) exhibiting dependence on tobacco. Notably, 4% had a history of dependence but were currently abstinent, underscoring the challenges and complexities in managing tobacco dependence among psychiatric patients.

Reasons and perceptions of tobacco use among psychiatric patients

Our study highlighted key reasons for tobacco use among psychiatric patients, including peer influence, experimentation, and stress relief, with variations among different user groups. Most exclusive smokers (80%) recognized tobacco as psychoactive, compared to 67.1% of smokeless users and 75.8% of dual users. Swetha P et al.¹⁰ similarly found peer influence as a primary reason for tobacco initiation, with varying awareness of tobacco's psychoactive properties among smokers and smokeless users, despite significant proportions believing they were not addicted. These findings illustrate diverse social influences and perceptions shaping tobacco use behaviours in psychiatric settings.

Tobacco use prevalence among psychiatric patients across different disorders

In the present study, tobacco use prevalence did not significantly differ across psychiatric disease groups, with similar usage rates among individuals with schizophrenia-related disorders (41.2%), mood disorders (46.7%), anxiety and stress-related disorders (47.1%), and behavioral syndromes (48.6%). Additionally, the patterns of tobacco use—smokeless tobacco, exclusive smoking, and dual use—showed no significant variation among these conditions. This contrasts with findings by Badekar et al.⁹, who reported higher tobacco use in neurotic, stress-related, and somatoform disorders (43.6%) compared to mood disorders (32.6%), schizophrenia-related disorders (34.3%), and behavioral syndromes (16.7%). Similarly, Swetha P et al.¹⁰ observed the

highest tobacco use in substance use disorders (75.6%), followed by mood disorders (45.2%), schizophrenia/psychotic disorders (27.7%), and neurotic, stress-related, somatoform disorders (1.2%). Kar et al. [6] noted a 52% prevalence of tobacco use among patients with severe mental illness (SMI), higher than those with common mental illness (CMI) at 28.9%. Most studies establish a strong association between smoking and schizophrenia, with nicotine's inhibitory effect on monoamine oxidase inhibitors increasing neurotransmitter levels and potentially enhancing mood. Disinhibition and substance-taking behaviour are common in manic episodes, and smoking is related to psychotic symptoms in mood disorders. [11,13]

Socio-demographic factors influencing tobacco use among psychiatric patients

This study reveals significant gender differences in tobacco use, with males (59.6%) far more likely to use tobacco than females (14.1%), yielding an odds ratio (OR) of 9.0. This exceeds the prevalence rates in Chennai, where male and female usage was 31.6% and 8%, respectively. Similar trends were observed in studies by Badekar et al.⁹ (79.4% male users vs. 50.3% female) and Kar et al.⁶ (58.85% male users vs. 7.21% female). Swetha P et al.¹⁰ also confirmed the significant association between tobacco use and male gender. It can be explained as in India, tobacco use among females is still socially unacceptable in many cultures.

Employment status significantly influenced tobacco use in this study, with employed individuals more likely to use tobacco (56.8%) compared to unemployed individuals (32.1%), yielding an OR of 2.85. This aligns with findings by Kar et al.⁶ (57.8% v/s 20.3%) and Swetha P et al. (58.1% v/s 41.7%), who also noted higher tobacco use among employed individuals. Economic independence and workplace culture in India, where tobacco use is common among laborers, shopkeepers, drivers, and carpenters, may explain this trend. Sharing tobacco among workmates is a common practice, further contributing to high prevalence rates among the employed. [14]

In the present study, marital status influenced tobacco use, with higher rates among divorced or widowed individuals (58.0%) compared to married (41.8%) and unmarried (43.3%) individuals, yielding an OR of 1.88. Educational level and employment status also impacted tobacco use, with higher prevalence among those with primary or lesser education and unemployed individuals. Additionally, tobacco use was more common in rural areas (52.8%) than in semi-urban/urban areas (40.6%), with an OR of 1.63.

Swetha P et al.¹⁰ found higher tobacco use rates among married individuals, though no significant links with other socio-demographic factors were

observed. Kar et al.⁶ reported higher mean age for tobacco users (35.24 years) compared to non-users (29.53 years) and a prevalence of primary education among both groups. Most patients were Hindu, and around 12% had a positive family history of psychiatric illness. Gupta et al. [15] noted higher tobacco use among employed and unmarried patients, while Chandra et al. [16] observed greater nicotine dependence among older, less-educated men.

High-risk behaviours and health concerns among psychiatric patients

Our study identified high-risk behaviors among psychiatric patients, including suicide attempts (29.5%), previous hospitalizations (46%), use of other psychoactive substances (46.5%), and substance use disorders (21.75%). Swetha P et al.¹⁰ similarly reported high rates of suicide attempts (67%), hospitalizations (54%), and psychoactive substance use (43.5%). In our study, patients using other psychoactive substances had a higher prevalence of tobacco use (72.6%) compared to those without substance use (21.0%), with an OR of 9.94. Kar et al.⁶ found 57% of current tobacco users also used other psychoactive substances, versus 5.5% of non-users.

Recent studies confirm the association between tobacco use and other substance use, with smoking prevalent in 77% to 88% of patients with substance use problems. [17–19] Nicotine and other psychoactive drugs share a dopamine-related dependence mechanism, and genetic factors link mental illnesses like alcohol and tobacco dependence. Tobacco use, considered a gateway drug, can hinder quitting other substances. Nicotine induces cytochrome P450 (CYP1A2), affecting the metabolism of psychotropic medications and hampering psychiatric treatment, emphasizing the importance of managing tobacco use alongside primary psychiatric conditions. [17–19] Our study found no significant differences in tobacco use related to a history of suicide attempts or previous hospitalizations.

Tobacco craving and motivation to quit among psychiatric patients

In the present study, both SMI and CMI groups exhibited moderate tobacco craving, with median scores of 47.0 and 46.0, respectively, showing no significant difference between the groups. Similarly, Badekar et al.⁹ found no differences in craving between SMI and CMDs, with smokers experiencing higher craving levels compared to smokeless tobacco users.

Patients with mental illness show motivation to quit tobacco, influenced by cultural acceptance of smokeless tobacco and awareness of smoking-related harms. This motivation parallels that of

individuals without mental illness, though it can vary across diagnostic groups. Despite their willingness, patients often receive fewer interventions, as health workers perceive quitting as more challenging due to multiple impairments. [20,21]

Suboptimal management of tobacco use in psychiatric care

Our study revealed significant deficiencies in managing tobacco use among psychiatric patients. Despite high rates of early initiation (31.7%) and nicotine dependence among users (32.2%), a large proportion were not screened (44.4%), and few advised to quit (37.2%), provided cessation assistance (23.9%), or offered nicotine replacement therapies (21.1%) or anti-craving medications.

Similar gaps were observed in the study of Badekar A et al.⁹, reflecting a broader issue in India where smokeless tobacco users, especially, receive inadequate intervention. Psychiatrists, despite their training in motivational interviewing, face barriers such as diagnostic overshadowing, competing clinical priorities, perceived incompetence, and time constraints when addressing tobacco use in practice.

Conclusion

The prevalence of tobacco use among psychiatric patients was notably high at 45%. Schizophrenia-related disorders was more prevalent (38.3%) compared to mood disorders (26.3%), behavioural syndromes (18.0%) and anxiety and stress-related disorders (17.5%). There were no significant differences in tobacco use prevalence or patterns across patients with different psychiatric disease. Higher tobacco use was observed among male, divorced or widowed individuals, those with lower education, employed individuals, and rural residents. Tobacco use was strongly associated with other psychoactive substance use. Despite the psychiatric setting, the assessment and implementation of interventions for tobacco cessation or reduction remained suboptimal. There is a need to enhance screening and implement targeted cessation programs for high-risk groups. Training healthcare providers on cessation strategies and utilizing inpatient admissions for screening and intervention opportunities are also essential.

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